

Simple and facile synthesis of (*E*)-9-hexadecen-1,16-olide (isoambrettolide) and dimethyl (*E*)-2-undecen-1,11-dioate, a juvenile hormone

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Abstract : (*E*)-9-Hexadecen-1,16-olide (isoambrettolide) possessing musk-like odour is used as fixative in perfumery formulations. It has been synthesized from *threo*-aleuritic acid (9,10,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid) by simple procedure. The compound showed antibacterial activity.

Synthesis of dimethyl (*E*)-2-undecen-1,11-dioate was achieved for the first time from *threo*-aleuritic acid, the major component of lac resin, and its bioassay has been reported.

Keywords : *threo*-Aleuritic acid, isoambrettolide, antibacterial activity, dimethyl (*E*)-2-undecen-1,11-dioate, juvenile hormone (JH).

Introduction

Lac, commercially known as shellac is a product of commerce, yielding resin, dye and wax. It is derived from lac insect cultured on specific trees called lac host trees. The major constituent acid of lac resin is aleuritic acid (1)¹, naturally occurring in *threo* form, which can easily be obtained by alkaline hydrolysis of shellac which is produced in large quantity in India.

Aleuritic acid (9,10,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid) has several handles for chemical manipulation, therefore can give variety of compounds of diverse interest. It had earlier been used by different workers²⁻⁹ for synthesis of isoambrettolide, possessing musk-like odour which is used as fixative in perfumery formulations. The compound showed antibacterial activity¹⁰⁻¹³. It was also used for synthesis of a number of compounds like ambrettolide¹⁴, exaltone¹⁵ etc. for use in perfumery industry and bioactive compounds like insect sex pheromones¹⁶, plant growth regulators¹⁷, nematicides¹⁸, insect repellants¹⁹, juvenile hormone analogue²⁰ etc.

A simple synthesis of compounds 4 and 7 using aleuritic acid as the starting material is reported here.

threo-Aleuritic acid on treatment with imidazole, chlorodiphenylphosphine and toluene in 1,4-dioxane for

Reaction sequences :

2 h yielded 16-hydroxy-(*E*)-9-hexadecenoic acid (**2**) in quantitative yield, which was esterified with dry methanol containing $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ to obtain methyl 16-hydroxy-(*E*)-9-hexadecenoate (**3**). Distillation of **3** with $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ resulted in the formation of compound **4**.

threo-Aleuritic acid, on periodate oxidation²¹ yielded **5** as one of the products, which on treatment with malonic acid in the presence of dry pyridine yielded (*E*)-2-undecen-1,11-dioic acid (**6**). It was esterified with dry methanol containing catalytic amount of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ on a steam bath for 15 min to obtain dimethyl (*E*)-2-undecen-1,11-dioate (**7**) in quantitative yield.

Experimental

Melting and boiling point reported are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer (90 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a JMS D-300 spectrophotometer. The compounds were routinely checked for their purity by TLC.

16-Hydroxy-(E)-9-hexadecenoic acid (2) : *threo*-Aleuritic acid (m.p. 100–101 °C, 6.2 g) was dissolved in 1,4-dioxane (50 ml), imidazole (4.4 g), chlorodiphenylphosphine (6.6 g) and iodine (7.9 g) were then added with stirring. After 4 h the reaction mixture was diluted with water, washed with aq. sodium thiosulphate (5%, 100 ml), followed by aq. Na_2CO_3 (5%, 100 ml). Sodium carbonate extract was acidified with 10% H_2SO_4 and its usual work-up with EtOAc furnished **2** as a solid, which was recrystallized from ether-pet. ether (40–60 °C), m.p. 69–70 °C (yield 92%); ν_{max} : 3250 (-OH), 1705 and 968

(*E*)
 cm^{-1} (CH = CH) (Found : C, 71.2; H, 11.4. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_3$: C, 71.1; H, 11.2%).

Methyl-16-hydroxy-(E)-9-hexadecenoate (3) : The above unsaturated acid (5.0 g) was esterified with dry methanol (50 ml) containing catalytic amount of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ on steam bath for 30 min. Usual work-up with ether afforded **3** as a liquid (4.7 g), which was purified by column chromatography using ether as eluent; ν_{max} : 3260 (-OH), 1728 (C=O of ester carbonyl), 970 cm^{-1}

(*E*)
(CH = CH) (Found : C, 72.1; H, 11.1. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 72.1; H, 11.2%).

Isoambrettolide (4) : The foregoing ester (4.4 g) was distilled with $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.4 g) at a bath temperature 220–320 °C/0.27 mm. The distillate (2.7 g) was dissolved in ether (100 ml) and washed with aq. Na_2CO_3 (5%, 100 ml) followed by water. The ethereal extract was washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent gave crude isoambrettolide, which was purified by distillation at 115–116 °C/0.2 mm, yield 60.0%; ν_{max} : 1731.8

(*E*)
(C=O in a macrocyclic lactone), 971.9 cm^{-1} (CH = CH); ¹H NMR : 1.28 (18H, br s, $-(\text{CH}_2)_n-$), 2.0 (4H, br, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.3 (2H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}$), 5.27–5.43 (2H, m, CH-CH); MS (*m/z*) : 252 (M^+ , 16.9), 208, 182 (1.7), 154 (2.0), 84, 70.

9-Oxononanoic acid (5) : *threo*-Aleuritic acid (32.0 g, 0.105 mol) was treated with NaOH solution (4.2 g, 0.105 mol) in water (126 ml). Chloroform (126 ml) was added followed by NaIO_4 (26.9 g, 0.125 mol) in lots for 15 min. The solution was then shaken at 40 °C for another 15 min and processed following the reported procedure²¹ to yield **5** as a liquid (16.7 g), purified by column chromatography with diethyl ether as eluent; ν_{max} : 1725 (-C=O), 1700 cm^{-1} (COOH); ¹H NMR : 1.11–1.8 (10H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$), 2.3 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CHO}$), 9.54 (1H, t, -CHO), 9.86 (1H, bs, -COOH).

(*E*)-2-Undecen-1,11-dioic acid (**6**) : The above compound (3.0 g) was heated on a steam bath with malonic acid (3.0 g) in dry pyridine (10 ml) till the effervescence of CO_2 ceased. Usual work-up with diethyl ether afforded the desired compound as a solid (2.8 g). It was crystallized from MeOH (m.p. 97–99 °C); ν_{max} : 1705 (-COOH),

(*E*)
970 cm^{-1} (CH = CH) (Found : C, 61.6; H, 8.4. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 61.7; H, 8.4%).

Dimethyl (E)-2-undecen-1,11-dioate (7) : The foregoing unsaturated acid (2.0 g) was esterified with dry methanol (25 ml) containing catalytic amount of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ on a steam bath for 15 min. Usual work-up followed by extraction with diethyl ether afforded the desired compound as a liquid (1.9 g) which was purified by column chromatography using diethyl ether as eluent; ν_{max} : 1725

(*E*)
(-COOCH₃), 968 cm^{-1} (CH = CH) (Found : C, 64.4; H, 9.0. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 64.4; H, 9.1%).

Biological activity of isoambrettolide (4) :

Antibacterial activity^{10,11} :

Isoambrettolide (**4**) was tested *in vitro* for antibacte-

rial activity^{12,13} against all *Shigella spp*, *Shigella dysenteriae 2*, *Shigella dysenteriae 9*, *Shigella flexneritype 6E03489*, *Shigella boydii B22461*, *Shigella sonenii BCH 217*, *Shigella sonenii BCH 217*, *Shigella sonenii NK 376*. Compound 4 showed marked activity. The MIC was found to be 50 µg/ml excepting *Shigella boydii B22416* where MIC was 100 µg/ml. Moderate sensitive to Gram-negative strains *Escherichia coli* ETEC LTS7 and *Escherichia coli* ATCC 10536 with an MIC of 100 µg/ml was observed. The zone of inhibition was recorded after 24 h at 37 °C {O* – control (DMSO)}.

Biological activity of compound 7 :

Evaluation of dimethyl (*E*)-2-undecen-1,11-dioate (7) for its juvenile hormone (JH) activity against *Helicoverpa armigera* (cotton boll worm) was done.

(a) Stage tested : Pupae

(b) Method of application : Topical

(c) Number of treatment : 5

(d) Number of replication : 1

(e) Number of pupae/treatment : 10

Treatment details :

Dilution : 200 µL of sample + 1500 µL of acetone.

Observations : Recorded malformation of pupae and adults

Treatments	No. of pupae treated	No. of pupae died	No. of adult emerged	No. of malformed adults
T ₁ -10 µL	10	0	10	2
T ₂ -20 µL	10	0	10	3
T ₃ -30 µL	10	1	9	2
T ₄ -40 µL	10	0	10	5
T ₅ -Control (acetone)	10	0	10	0

Interpretation of results :

Juvenile hormone regulates many developmental and physiological events in insects, viz. insect development, metamorphosis and reproduction. Deficiency and excess of the same will therefore interfere with normal insect development. The results obtained indicated that at a dose of 40 µL/topical application of 7 resulted in 50% malformed adults. This points to the fact that the compound may be exhibiting JH like activity at this concentration. Therefore, dimethyl (*E*)-2-undecen-1,11-dioate may be used as a substitute for JH in insect related works.

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